

USAGE OF SILENT WAY METHOD IN TEACHING ENGLISH FOR INTERMEDIATE LEVELS

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Annotation. This paper examines the role of silent way method in teaching English for intermediate levels, moreover, features of silent way method such as focus on discovery, creativity, problem solving and the use of accompanying materials in teaching process have been analysed in this work.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'rta darajali o'qitishda "silent way" usulining o'rni ko'rib chiqiladi, bundan tashqari, bu ishda "silent way" usulining kashfiyotga e'tibor qaratish, ijodkorlik, muammolarni hal qilish va o'qitish jarayonida qo'shimcha materiallardan foydalanish kabi xususiyatlari tahlil qilingan.

Аннотация. В данной статье исследуется роль метода молчания в обучении английскому языку для среднего уровня, кроме того, в этой работе были проанализированы особенности метода молчания, такие как ориентация на открытие, творчество, решение проблем и использование сопутствующих материалов в учебном процессе.

Key words: silent way method, intermediate levels, focus on discovery, creativity, problem solving.

Kalit so'zlar: "silent way", o'rta darajalar, kashfiyotga e'tibor qaratish, ijodkorlik, muammolarni hal qilish.

Ключевые слова: метод молчания, среднего уровня, ориентация на открытие,

творчество, решение проблем.

Any language in the world has its own structure and each one has several peculiarities of its own. There are a methods that can teach learners peculiarities of a language with different ways. Method is the way of learning in teaching process. According to Brown (2000, p. 16), a set of classroom specifications for reaching the objective of learning is method.

The Silent Way is the name of a method of language teaching created by Caleb Gattegno. The silent way is called because “the aim of the teacher is to say as little as possible in order can be in control of what she wants to say” (Nosrati, Karimi, Malekian & Hariri, 2013, p. 210). In this method, the students are the center of the learning process, and the teacher should be largely silent. In other word, the teacher should be less talk during learning activity in the classroom, and the learners are encouraged to be more active in producing language (Richard & Rodger, 1986, p. 99). In addition, students are responsible for their own work. Each method has particular characteristic that shows the feature of that method. A general characteristic in silent way method is the teacher less talk during teaching activity. The silent way method also have elements, which drawing the activity of teaching in the classroom. The Silent Way makes use of some specialized teaching materials: coloured Cuisenaire rods, the sound-colour chart, word charts, and Fidel charts. According to Richard & Rodger (1986, p. 99), the particularly elements used in silent way method are colour charts and the coloured Cuisenaire rods. In addition, Brown also described the material of silent way in a language classroom is utilized a set of Cuisenaire rods-small coloured rods of varying lengths and a series of colourful wall charts (2000, p. 29). The Cuisenaire rods are wooden, and come in ten different lengths, but identical cross-section; each length has its own assigned colour. The procedure of silent way method in teaching language is giving instruction. For

example, in teaching vowel sound, teacher will stick five blocks of vowel sound (a,i,u,e,o) on the whiteboard with different colours. Then, the teacher will point each letter without saying the sound for the second times. In the third time, she will mention the sound of the letter. The teacher only gives the instruction to students and they will response it. The intermediate level students will repeat the sound by themselves when teacher points the block of vowel sound.

With the Silent Way, intermediate level students are engaged in the learning process, discovering words and sounds instead of having these drilled into them. Intermediate level students become more engaged and invested in the process as they assume more responsibility for their own learning, and tasks have more relevance. The Intermediate level students lead to greater attention, more participate and good behavior. In intermediate level students classroom the teacher can apply the various method include the silent way method. The intermediate level students express their ideas or creativity directly when the teacher gives instructions or clues without asking their name. In this method, the students were demanded to build a critical thinking in guessing what the information taught by the teacher.

The silent way method is taken from match method. Thus, this study tries to gain the information about students' opinion on silent way method implemented in the classroom, whether it is effective or have to add some activity to make the method appropriate with learning English.

Methods have an important role in language teaching. It is a design or systematic effort of teachers to determine a series plan in various parts of teaching learning process. Methods have many different definitions. According to Parel and Jain (2008, p. 71), method is a process of planning, technique of teaching, selection and grading language materials and items. As Brown described in his book, method as “an overall plan for systematic presentation of language based upon a selected 9 approach” (2000, p. 14). Therefore, the use of methods in teaching language

becomes an influential thing on learning process. There are many kinds of method that can be used in teaching language. One of them is silent way method.

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